

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₄	224	86
1b	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ IN ₂ O ₆	210	85
1c	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₆	206	85
2a	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₅	94	81
2b	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₅	196	79
2c	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₇	152	73
2d	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₄	136	79
2e	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ BrN ₄ O ₄	113	72
2f	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ IN ₄ O ₄	142	83
2g	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ IN ₄ O ₄	159	82
2h	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ IN ₄ O ₆	119	70
2i	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ IN ₄ O ₆	126	77
2j	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ IN ₄ O ₆	122	76
2k	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₄	133	80
2l	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₄	192	74
2m	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₆	131	73
2n	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₆	126	81
2o	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ BrN ₄ O ₆	180	74

*All the compounds showed satisfactory results for N analyses.

were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 5 compounds (2b, c, e, f, k) active against *E. coli*; thus 3 compounds (2e, f, k) were found active against both the species.

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Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of 2-Hydroxy-4,6-diphenylpyrimidines

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PYRIMIDINES have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities¹. With a view to getting better therapeutic activity, some new pyrimidines of type 4 were synthesised.

2-Hydroxyacetophenones (1) were condensed with benzoyl chloride or *p*-anisoyl chloride to get the respective *o*-aroyloxyacetophenones (2) which were then treated with KOH-pyridine to get 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethanes² (3). Compounds 3 were condensed with urea in ethylene glycol (solvent) to obtain 2-hydroxy-4-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidines³ (4) (Scheme 1). The structural assign-

Scheme 1

ment of the compounds was based on their elemental analyses and ir and pmr spectral data.

The ir spectra for all the compounds **3** revealed identical bands at 3 500–3 350 (OH), 1 640–1 620 (C=O conjugated) and 1 600–1 490 cm^{-1} (phenyl). The pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **3a**, showed signals at δ 2.20 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.60 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.8–5.6 (1H, s, OH) and 6.9–8 (8H, m, ArH). The ir spectra for the compounds **4** revealed identical bands at 3 450–3 300 (OH), 1 690–1 640 (C=N, pyrimidine). In the pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **4a**, signals have been observed at δ 2.56 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.8–5.2 (1H, s, OH) and 7.13–8.10 (8H, m, ArH).

Antibacterial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity using cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 5 mg ml^{-1} against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compounds **4h**, **4l** and **4p** were found inactive against both the organisms. Other compounds showed a moderate or weak activity against *S. aureus*. Compounds **4a** and **4k** showed a very strong inhibition and others showed a medium activity against *E. coli*.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd no	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M p °C	Yield %
4a	H	OCH_3	H	H	101	60
b	H	OCH_3	NO_2	H	135	70
c	H	OCH_3	Br	H	140	65
d	Br	OCH_3	NO_2	H	155	72
e	H	OC_2H_5	H	H	125	62
f	H	OC_2H_5	NO_2	H	168	73
g	H	OC_2H_5	Br	H	116	68
h	Br	OC_2H_5	NO_2	H	138	70
i	H	OCH_3	H	OCH_3	110	60
j	H	OCH_3	NO_2	OCH_3	175	75
k	H	OCH_3	B ₁	OCH_3	160	70
l	B ₁	OCH_3	NO_2	OCH_3	158	72
m	H	OC_2H_5	H	OCH_3	90	55
n	H	OC_2H_5	NO_2	OCH_3	180	72
o	H	OC_2H_5	Br	OCH_3	152	66
p	Br	OC_2H_5	NO_2	OCH_3	170	80

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (100 MHz) on a XL-100A spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

o-Aroyloxyacetophenone (2a–h): 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (**1**; 0.1 mol), dissolved in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (75 ml) was treated with redistilled benzoyl chloride (0.1 mol) and the mixture shaken vigorously for 15–20 min. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

o-Aroyloxyacetophenone (2i–p): 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (**1**; 0.1 mol) and anisic acid (0.11 mol) were dissolved in dry pyridine (60 ml). The solution

was kept in a cold water-bath and phosphorous oxychloride (0.07 mol) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring maintaining the temperature below 50°. After 3 h the mixture was decomposed by cold dilute HCl (1 : 1). The resulting solid was washed with water and 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. Their alcoholic solutions did not give colour with FeCl_3 solution.

2'-Hydroxydibenzoylmethane (3a–p): A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol), dry pyridine (25 ml) and powdered KOH (0.05 mol) was stirred for about 30 min and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture on acidification with dilute HCl gave a yellow solid which was washed with 10% bicarbonate solution followed by water and recrystallised from ethanol. It gave deep violet colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-4-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (4a–p): A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol) and urea (0.01 mol) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then poured into cold water with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table I).

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Reaction of Ethylchloroformate with 1-Alkyl/ Aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets in Presence of Ketones

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new *s*-triazine derivatives as potential antimicrobial agents¹, we now report an interesting reaction of ethyl chloroformate with dithiobiurets (**1**) in the